

PROBLEMS OF CLASSIFICATION OF TERMS IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This article discusses the problems of classification of terms, which is one of the current problems in linguistics today. Also, the theoretical basis of the classification of terms is explained.

Key words: Linguistics, term, classification linguistics, scientific analysis, extralinguistics, terminological systems.

Introduction:

As a complex and multifaceted phenomenon, the term has not lost its interest, on the contrary, it has a special place in the linguistics of the beginning of the 21st century. At the same time, scientists are researching the theoretical and practical problems related to the study of its individual types as a whole.

As N.V. Serbinovskaya rightly recognized, *"The terminological field changes over time, reflecting the achievements of new knowledge; some units in its content disappear and new ones appear, terms move within the terminological field, are transferred to other semantic groups, occupy a new position"*¹.

Despite the fact that a lot of terminological research has been carried out, the problems of classification of terms, in particular, the problems of distinguishing their special types used in interdisciplinary integration, remain relevant. "It serves as a basis for different classification and description of the specific aspects of the terms." As V.P. Danielko rightly stated: "The special lexicon of linguistics is characterized by the increasingly high level of systematicity of its separate links, that is, its branch systems. This systematicity is, on the one hand, the existence of classifications of certain concepts on the basis of established principles, and on the other hand, it is conditioned by the participation of the science of linguistics in the integration of various terminological systems into its structure"².

The possibility and necessity of classifying the concepts expressed in terminology is considered as a different feature of the terminological lexicon compared to the national language. Because the terms are related to a certain scientific concept, scientific discoveries, researches and theoretical and practical results are expressed in them. Terms are considered means of communication in special professional fields, describing events, concepts, phenomena occurring in one or another professional field. This naturally leads to attempts by domestic and foreign scientists to regulate, unify and systematize terms. Classification and description of terms by special fields is important: it reflects the level of gradual development of science and social fields in a certain period. The point is that the term taken in isolation does not acquire meaning outside of the context. The term participates in the terminological

¹ Serbinovskaya N.V. Formation and development of the terminological field "marketing" in the Russian language: Author's abstract. diss. ...cand. Philol. nauk.-Rostov-on-Don, 2008.-25p.

² Danilenko V.P. Russian terminology. Experience in linguistic analysis.-M.: Nauka, 1977.-246 p.

system, that is, in its integration with the terms of its own system or other special, small (specialized) systems. For example, when used in "economy", "banking", "accounting-audit", "credit" and other similar fields, it acquires uniqueness and becomes a special field term. Therefore, the relationship of the term, the correct understanding of its essence as a term is formed by mastering the term system that provides one or another aspect of the life of the society.

Experts have different opinions about the need to create a classification system in order to organize and systematize terminologies. For example, according to Sven Jakobson: "the absence of standardization in the terminology of social sciences leads to an unlimited increase of new concepts in a number of disciplines." And Juan Sager states: The terminological fields of special science fields should be different from the lexical fields of the general language³.

In the article "Three types of terminologies", the Swedish linguist Sven Jakobson distinguishes the following three types of terminology, pointing out that the systematic standardization of terminology, that is, strengthening of the term in the field of academic or professional activity.

- academic or professional terminology that is subject to standardization, prevents misinterpretation, and is highly compatible as a result of terms and extralinguistic factors;
- academic or professional terminology that has a greater impact on the active use of the term by the user;
- Terminology that appears in the periphery of the terminological system and universal language, despite attempts to standardize it, in most cases has the same development direction as ordinary language.

According to the sources, it is noted that the terminologies belonging to the first type are characteristic for science and technology.

V. M. Leychik, while analyzing the concepts of Western terminology, first of all points out that the system of concepts formed by E. Wuster and the school of his followers plays an important role based on them. "If it consists only of "vertical relations", it is called a "divisional system" (divisional system) and is considered hierarchical according to the characteristics of its gradual development. If the system of concepts consists not only of vertical relations, but also of absolute "novertical relations", it is considered a "combinatorial system" and is polyhierarchical according to its formal properties. In the second case, the logical properties of such a "classification", its classification methods and principles are different, for example, the method of consistently classifying terminological concepts is different from each other⁴.

V.V. Kasyanov reacted to the works of Anglo-American researchers in the field of terminology in this way: the similarity of the analyzed works can be seen in the process of analyzing the sources and methods of formation of terms. This situation is manifested in the separation of the semantic group of terms in English: if some of the terms are borrowed from the general literary language; some are borrowed from other languages; some of them are international words formed from international elements through the method of copying.

³ Sager J. Variability of the term and its substitution in scientific Russian-language and German-language text: Author's abstract. diss. ...cand. Philol. nauk.-Ekaterinburg: 2004.-23 p.

⁴ Leichik V.M., Shelov S.D. Linguistic problems of terminology and scientific and technical translation. Part II. Issue 18.-M., 1990.-80 p.

In the terminological literature published in the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, there were different approaches and perspectives on the classification of terms. The terms considered a multifaceted phenomenon are divided into different classifications according to logical, linguistic, scientific and other principles. These classifications generally determine the role and place of terms in the scientific, economic, political, management and other spheres of society. "When systematizing terms, they can be lexically-semantically grouped according to their content, form, functional function, internal and external signs of the language. Naturally, all classifications listed in the study are important. At the same time, separate terms from related units; on the other hand, on the basis of terminological principles, it is appropriate to group all their types according to semantic signs.

How to implement the ideas of classification and description of the terminological system according to the criteria of the regulation of terms depends to a large extent on the structural conglomerate (mixture) of the lexicon of the field. This can be understood as structuring (grouping of concepts, then semantically grouping of relevant terms) as a logical method of separating classified terms according to different bases (D.S.Lotte, T.L.Kandelaki). "By system, we understand the terminological elements as a whole with the help of certain lexical-semantic relations. Systematicity, the concepts of classification and description, and the systematicity of terminology are closely related to the systematicity of knowledge in a particular field.

T.L.Kandelaki and G.G.Samburova emphasize that various linguistic signs play an important role in the formation of the logical-semantic structure of the terminology, and as a result of the analysis of the work carried out in this regard, they distinguish two cases:

1. Each linguistic sign used in the classification can be applied to all the concepts or objects being classified.
2. There are signs that can be applied to certain parts of concepts and objects.

T.L. Kandelaki and G.G. In the first case, Samburova thinks about the independence of linguistic signs and the resulting "parallel type classification", and in the second case, the interdependence of signs, as well as the "consistency type classification".

In addition to the social and humanitarian sciences, many specialists addressed the problem of maintaining (creating), classifying, and using the terms correctly in the field of natural sciences. The scope of this activity in the field of linguistics is extensive. However, as a result of the analysis of all of them, the general opinion is explained by the need to clearly distinguish specific semantic groups of terminological systems that make up terminological principles, concepts and categories, and to develop them from a typological point of view. For example, A.N. According to Baranov, there are three main signs based on the classification of terms: the field of science, which is the source for mastering terminological units; a set of heuristic approaches imposed on industry experts in the process of mastering terms; areas of active use of terms⁵. In fact, most linguists note that in the issue of creating (generating) terms and classifying them, the specific features of form and meaning are relevant.

A complete overview of existing classifications is provided by V.M. Leychik, the author has developed 15 main expressed tables for the separation of concepts. Based on them, 10 types of classification used by terminologists were formed.

⁵ Baranov A.N. Introduction to Applied Linguistics. -M.: 2003.-360 p.

The variety of classifications allows today's specialists to combine and vary their different types, create their own hybrid classifications within the framework of researching terminological fields. According to O. L. Ariskina: all formed models have the right to exist due to the acceptance of authorship of the world, science, thinking, etc. T.V. Shetle, in his research on the systematicity of banking terminology, shows the impartiality of objective assessment in the creation and development of the terminology of social and humanitarian sciences.

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